

HOLIDAYS ARE THE MIRROR OF FOLK CULTURE

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Abstract

In the social and cultural life of every nation, age-old traditions, customs, rituals and holidays have a special place. They appear as a unique phenomenon of people's lifestyle. Usually, the term "holiday" means the celebration of an important event or date by a large number of people, in an upbeat spirit, with joy. The holiday is a continuation, an important part of life. It is not difficult to know the level of development of the people by looking at their celebrations. In particular, holidays can give a vivid picture of the social, economic and cultural situation of the country. Because holidays are a mirror that reflects the best aspects of social life. One of the most remarkable aspects of the holidays of the Uzbek people is their *nature* and *work* is related to. From the first days of our independence, restoring the priceless heritage and national traditions created by our ancestors has become an extremely important task that has risen to the level of state policy.

Keywords: "Traditional holidays", "new traditions", melon sali, religious beliefs, family rituals, ecology, harvest wedding, Mehrjan, Nowruz.

INTRODUCTION

In the social and cultural life of every nation, age-old traditions, customs, ceremonies and holidays have a special place. They appear as a unique phenomenon of people's lifestyle. The terms "Tradition", "Ritual", "Holiday" are not fixed concepts. Under the influence of the development of time and changes in life, the content of concepts also expands. Due to changes in social life, traditions and holidays that are no longer in demand are gradually being forgotten. Traditions that are essentially popular and have social weight will develop. For example, Navruz, Melon, Lola, etc. holidays have been living for centuries because they meet modern requirements. The change of people's life creates the corresponding traditions. In recent years, many social and personal - family traditions, ceremonies and holidays have appeared in the life of the Uzbek people, which did not exist before. Recently, the words "traditional holidays" and "new holidays" have been used in scientific literature and periodicals. "Traditional holidays" means ancient cultural and public events regularly held at a certain time - flower festival, Lola sali, melon sali, threshing wedding. Because they are folk holidays that have existed since ancient times. "New traditions" are events that are just coming into our lives and have just started in places. The holiday helps to deeply understand the paths traveled by humanity, to be proud of victories, to make plans for tomorrow, to hope for the future. Therefore, on the eve of the holiday, people congratulate each other and express good wishes. Holidays are a "mirror" that reflects the unique values of each nation. For example, during the holiday, people wear beautiful clothes, prepare delicious food, and show off their skills. Everyone is in a high mood that day. On the day of the holiday, a certain

level of closeness and cooperation is created between people than on other days. In the past, on this day, everyone ate from the same pot, watched the same show, and went for a walk in the same park. Bayram is an important and major event in the educational system. Holidays play an important role in the education of young people as they embody, preserve and develop the best traditions, customs and moral rules of the people.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Usually, the term "holiday" refers to the celebration of an important event, event, date by a large number of people, in an upbeat spirit, with joy. Therefore, Beruni calls holidays "the most important days" in life, Mahmud Kashgari describes them as "the day of joy and happiness". "Holiday," writes A.I. Mazayev, - this is an ideal life at a certain time." During the holidays, people "for a short time, feel free from daily work, worries, sadness, anger, dependence, debts, - says M. Kadyrov. "The social, political and cultural significance of holidays is determined by the fact that," writes Professor E.B. Sogolov, - it is a unique demonstration of success achieved in life based on the support of important traditions. Because all institutions and enterprises demonstrate their achievements on the occasion of the holiday. "It's a holiday," says A.I. Arnoldov, embodies the most valuable treasures collected in the treasury of world culture. Therefore, holidays are one of the most important forms of human culture, and are considered the most effective means of development of human society. Some holidays are declared public holidays. In our country, 9 days are designated as holidays to celebrate major holidays. Also, certain professional days are set to be held on Sundays. Researcher E.V. Sogolov considers holidays to be the best among all forms of recreation. Because the most effective forms of recreation are embodied in holiday events. Another distinctive feature of the holidays is the participation of the public in them. First of all, the holiday is organized for many people and it takes place directly with the participation of many people. In theaters, concert halls, television shows, and radio broadcasts, the public plays the role of spectators and listeners, while people take part in holidays as active participants. Everyone can show off their skills at the holidays. People observe the festive events as participants and can express their reaction to the events.

RESULTS

The essence of holidays depends on their content and idea. The content, the idea is the basis of every holiday, figuratively speaking, its "soul" and "blood". In the historical process, the idea of the meaning of holidays appeared and changed and developed on the basis of people's thoughts, pains, dreams and hopes. Both colonizers and local rulers tried to inculcate their ideas in the holidays. For example, colonialists tried to inculcate their ideology or Islamic leaders into religious ideas in Nowruz and Mehrjan. The Soviets tried to enrich the Harvest Festival with socialist ideas. Ideas instilled with violence have damaged the essence and form of holidays. This has weakened people's interest in holidays. Because of this, some holidays have been forgotten or lost. The rulers tried to ban them when their ideas could not be absorbed into the customs and holidays of the people. However, with the emergence of favorable conditions, "spirit" entered the content of the holidays again. In particular, during the period of independence, such an opportunity was created that the holidays satisfying the natural needs of the people were revived, enriched with a new content and a new idea. It should be said with pride that Uzbekistan's experience in organizing holidays is recognized as the most advanced in the CIS. Not only ourselves, but the whole world recognizes our efforts to restore the heritage of our ancestors. Experts visiting from many countries of the world,

such as America, Norway, Holland, France, Germany, Turkey, to study our extensive work in this regard, admire our efforts to restore our traditional culture, including our holidays.

DISCUSSION

It is not difficult to know the level of development of the people by looking at their celebrations. In particular, holidays can give a vivid picture of the social, economic and cultural situation of the country. Because holidays are a mirror that reflects the best aspects of social life. Holidays of a well-developed nation will also be blessed. In addition to the great historical, spiritual, scientific heritage, architectural monuments, art, and literature of their ancestors, the Uzbek people are also proud of the fact that they have thousands of years of festive and ceremonial culture. Uzbek holidays were created based on the social and spiritual needs of our ancestors during the long development process. Their minds passed from generation to generation depending on the environment, nature, labor process and progressed on the basis of their creative activity. It has become a priceless social and cultural heritage embodying the thoughts, dreams, experiences, achievements and other values of the ancestors. However, this historical heritage of Uzbek people's holidays has not been specially studied yet. The main reason for this was that during the Soviet period, the study of national holidays was officially and unofficially prohibited, and only new Soviet holidays could be studied. Due to independence, opportunities to study Uzbek traditions are opening up. Some issues of national traditions and national holidays have begun to be researched. The period of special and authentic study of the holidays of the Uzbek people has come. This requires a comprehensive study of our heritage, which has not been appreciated at the time, from the historical, political, philosophical, moral, ethnological, and cultural perspectives. At the same time, there are a number of important aspects of Uzbek holidays that should be noted. First of all, it is necessary to study the history of the holidays of the Uzbek people. Because until now, the holidays of the Uzbek people, which have a long history, have not been taken as a special object of research. It is known that Central Asia is one of the oldest centers of human culture. Archaeological research shows that people have been living in this area for 1 million years. Therefore, the culture of the local population, including the customs of the Uzbek people, should be studied covering not only centuries, but also hundreds of thousands of years. A separate study of the history of Uzbek holidays into the oldest period, the ancient period, the middle ages, the new centuries and the 20th century will greatly benefit the generalization of experiences specific to each period.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, I can say that since the first days of our independence, the restoration of the priceless heritage and folk traditions created by our ancestors has become an extremely important task that has risen to the level of state policy. The holidays of Uzbekistan are gaining international importance. Because for more than 10 years, there have been remarkable experiences in organizing holidays in Uzbek style in our republic. However, the history, traditions and current state of Uzbek people's holidays have not been widely studied. It is a historical necessity to create a special monograph, scientific and popular book, textbooks and training manuals about the emergence, historical development, and problems of ancient and modern holidays. Because the people should know the history and traditions of the holidays that appeared in their homeland, were celebrated by their ancestors and are being celebrated now. It is difficult to find an individual, family or community that does not

celebrate the holidays. Every nation and state has its own holidays. In recent years, more and more universal holidays are celebrated at the international level.

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